

Organizational Development Diagnosis In The Health Adjutancy Department Of Mashhad Medical Sciences University From Perspectives Of The Managers And Experts And Presentation Of The Some Solutions

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Abstract:

Change and Development is a continuous aspect of human life. All organizations and companies must learn how to manage their change and development, otherwise the changes and different evolutions will determine their movement direction. Accordingly, the organizational diagnosis and understanding the causes of lack of organization change and development has been become a management necessity in organizations. In this study, the determinant factors on the inconveniences in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University were assessed by using the Weisbord's Organizational Diagnosis Model. The present study, in terms of purpose is descriptive and in terms of use type is empirical. For data collection we made use standardized questionnaire of Weisbord model. Statistical population is included all managers and administrators and experts that working in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University. 116 participants out Of all the people were selected as the sample of the study by using random sampling method. Methods of descriptive and inferential statistics were performed by using SPSS statistical software. Results of data analysis by using t-test, indicated that organization in the dimensions of goals, relationships and leadership has a better position than other dimensions and has damaged in the reward dimension. The highest correlation coefficient observed between dimensions of leadership, structure, relationships and attitude toward change with useful mechanisms.

Keywords: *organizational diagnosis, Weisbord model, organizational development, Mashhad Medical Sciences University.*

Introduction

Change and Development is a continuous aspect of human life. Nothing like development and change is not continuous. In organizations and institutions, the affairs trend toward changes is much more and this affects all parts of work process such as production, technology, systems and staff. All organizations and companies must learn how to manage the change and development, otherwise the changes and different evolutions will determine their movement direction and there is not another way. The survival key for any system is acceptance and adaptation with change. In other words, any system that can adapt itself to a changing environment, can continue its existence. In today's world where changes happen quickly, if organizations don't progress continuously or can't use advanced technology and don't react against changes of environmental factors, after of period, their life office will be closed (Robbins, Stephen, 1999).

For as much as the change and development is one of the largest properties of the organizations and institutions in the today's competitive field, technological changes or any other developments also require be managed. Organizational development pays more attention to the problems of people working in the organization. In the field of organization development is important pay attention to problems such as poor mentality, low productivity, poor quality goods and services, conflict between individuals, conflict between groups, unknown goals of long-term and short-term whether at the level of organization strategy and whether at the level of units goals, inappropriate leadership styles, poor team performance, inappropriate organizational structure, poor design of tasks, low attention to environmental demands, poor relationship with customer, conflict between the units goals and so on. In fact, in all cases where we could not optimally used from individuals, groups and organization, Organization development can improve conditions because organizational development is the process that pays more attention to culture, processes and used structure in a comprehensive system. (Moshabbaki, Asghar, 1998).

Despite the rich history of organization development topic and its importance, unfortunately, have been paid little attention to the issues of review, assessment and measurement of development amount and change in

organizational processes, particularly in the areas of health in the country level and few studies have been done in this area. Due to health conditions and the growth of non-communicable diseases in the country, health care increasingly goes towards the complexity and wide spreading, every day, if health system couldn't make change in the management of this system will not be able to development the organization according to health policy goals. Because change and development is associated with some uncertainty, so it affects the stability and security of staff and managers who are exposed to change. Hence it is obvious that at least the first change experience for employees of public and private organizations is not easy and some resistance to change will be natural. The public organizations study shows that employee resistance is not the only obstacle to the development and change of the organization and there are many factors that public organizations have paralyzed. Because steadiness and uniformity have greatly reduced the efficiency of our public and state organizations, it is essential to identify the barriers of change and development of the organizations and provide the solutions to overcome them (Vice-chancellor and secretary of the community,2004).

In this regard, to implement development projects in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University as one of the main pillars of change in the health system, conducting a fieldwork on the current status of organization in terms of development and change of processes and providing the strategies for improving and promoting it, is very essential.

Overview on the theoretical foundations

Theoretical background of Organizational Development

Organizational Development is a kind of strategy (organization improvement) that was introduced in the late 1950s and early 1960s. Its foundation is based on the insights and knowledge gained from group dynamics and theories and applications and can solve many important human problems of organization. The change and development can be considered as a change in environment, structure, technology or people in an organization (French, Vandals and Bell, Cecil H. 2013).

Organizational Development is a systematic and planned process that by using the values and principles of practical behavioral science in the organizations increases the individual and organizational effectiveness. In other words, it is the focus of the organizations discussion and contains changes that improve their performance and its aim is the change of entire system. Also, one of the most important achievements of organizational change is to provide guidelines for improving adaptation among individuals and organizations, between organization and the environment and ultimately, among the elements and components of its organization such as strategy, structure and processes. These guidelines will be implemented through programs and activities of change creation that their aim is to fix a problem in certain situations and problematic (Robbins, Stephen P. and David E. D Sanzou, 2015).

Organizational Development uses a set of methods for achieving the development and the realization of programs that will enhance an organization's ability to confront its rivals (Robbins, Stephen P. and David E. D Sanzou, 2015). Most interventions of organizational change involves the following steps: Data collection, diagnosis, organizational feedback, practical plans, implement, evaluation and if necessary, reconsideration (Sinaki, 2011).

Organizational diagnosis

Identifying problems is one of the first activities that is done in organizational development. In fact, diagnosis by using the lawful manner and an integral part of methodology validates organizational development. Diagnosis scope includes the accurate investigation of all systems and examination of problem details. Usually through diagnosis, the problems of organization are identified and then studied. So, the raised questions are as follows: What factor makes the work be done? What are the barriers to achieving organizational goals? And what should be done? (Chitsaz et al., 2004).

Organizational diagnosis is a comprehensive activity to uncover the truth and a prerequisite for organizational efforts. This method has been designed as an important factor in change and organizational improvement for the correct and appropriate action and help eliminate the blind spots of management. In diagnosis, major planned changes that are in interaction with organization can be effectively used for development purposes and before solving problem (Burke and Debra, 2015).

Organizational Development Models

The Organizational Development Models are the tools to help organizations to measure it for being in the path of the organizational excellence and balanced growth (Khodadad Kashi, Farhad, 2006). Including organizational change models can be mentioned the following models:

The Likert-system analysis model that examines organizational aspects of motivation, relationships, interaction, decision making, goal setting, control and performance (Likert, 1967). In the mid-1970s, an organizational design consultant named Marvin Weisbord presented its six box model as a diagnosis tool of the organizational effectiveness. Weisbord identified six areas or very important parts (goals, structure, payments, mechanisms of coordination and control, relationships and leadership) (Weisbord, 1976). Tushman-Nadler's compatibility or homogeneous model has been proposed with the aim of understanding the dynamics in an organization at the changes time. In this model, the organization includes the following four components: work (daily activities), staff (skills of people working in the organization), the official organization (structure and policies of the organization) and informal organization (unwritten activities such as values and norms) (Paul, 2015). McKinsey's 7S framework is another model that includes the seven variables of structure, strategy, systems, skills, procedures, personnel and common values (Watson, 2015). Galbrid's star model is a systemic and conceptual model about how the organization performance and includes five variables of strategy, structure, process, rewards and employees (Galbrid, 2014).

Experimental background

In a study entitled "Organizational diagnosis of project-oriented enterprises, study case: Development of Iran Water and Power Resources Company" was investigated by Behrouz Zarei and Yahya Chaghooee in 2014. Statistical population of the study is included all managers of mentioned company. Based on the research results, company in five main areas of strategy, systems, structure, personnel and organizational processes has the problems and inconveniences that the most problems have occurred in the structural part.

The conformity rate of the learning organization components based on Marquardt model was studied by Mohsen Zare Nazarzadeh et al., in Tehran Medical Sciences University in the winter 2014. Statistical population was consisted all librarians of libraries of Tehran Medical Sciences University with 50 participants. The research results showed that the mean of dynamic components of learning, organizational change, empowerment, knowledge management and application of technology in the libraries of Tehran Medical Sciences University is in the poor level.

A study entitled " Organizational Development and Strategic Intervention for Enterprise Sustainability in the investment: empirical evidence from Nigeria" was carried out by using the Weisbord's six-dimensional model by Kheiroddin Idris and his colleagues in 2014 in one of the hospitals in Nigeria. The sample size was 67. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between teamwork and performance.

In a study entitled " Evaluate the status of diagnosis components based on the developed Weisbord's six-dimensional model in the Mehr Eghtesad Bank of Isfahan province "was carried out by using the Weisbord's six-dimensional model by Meysam Shoeib in 2015. Statistical population was included 488 participants from all employees of Mehr Eghtesad Bank of the Isfahan province. 217 participants out of all the population were selected as the statistically sample. The results showed that only rewards variable is in a bad situation and other variables are at an appropriate level.

Also, a study with the aim of examining strengths and weaknesses of the Directorate General of Ports and Maritime of Mazandaran province based on the Weisbord model was conducted by Mohsen Salarian and colleagues in 2015. Statistical population was included 167 participants from all employees of the Directorate General of Ports and Maritime of Mazandaran province with at least a bachelor's degree. 115 participants out of all the population were randomly selected as the statistically sample. Results showed that the dimensions of institutional mechanisms and processes, relationships, leadership and goals are in an appropriate condition and components of reward and organizational structure are in optimal condition.

A study with the aim of organizational diagnosis of the Chabahar Free Trade-Industrial Zone Organization by using the Weisbord model was conducted by Ataollah Dadgar and Abdolmalek Balochzahi in 2015. Statistical population was included all employees of the Chabahar Free Trade-Industrial Zone Organization. 166 participants out of all the population were selected as the statistically sample. The results generally show that the status of the Chabahar Free Trade-Industrial Zone organization in all studied aspects with the exception of the rewards has been assessed appropriate and good.

In a study entitled " Application Of Weisbord's Organizational Diagnosis Model, A Case of Pakistan Banking Industry " was carried out by Afia Saleem and Osman Ghani in 2013. 117 participants out of all the population were selected as the statistically sample. Research results showed that studied organization has the difficulties in the reward dimension while rest of model dimensions have not any problems in the organization.

A study for developing a quantitative detection framework by combining the Weisbord's six boxes model with the Persivsi's growth management model was carried out in China. 180 participants out of China's oil company employees were selected as the sample. The results showed that China's oil company is at the fourth stage from the quintuple stages of growth. In addition, the above effective factors that inhibit the growth within the organization include: the lack of interaction along with the energy and time; the lack of personal work units existence and poor splitting the work to achieve sustainable growth rate.

Research conceptual model

Each of the models identify the importance of different organizational aspects and examine them in diagnosis. Weisbord model has been approved and is applicable in our organizations because of comprehensiveness, compatibility with open systems (presence of foreign element and its mutual impact on organizations), emphasis on leadership element as center of gravity and key factor in the growth of the organizations and finally, mention simultaneously to elements of software, brainware and hardware. For this reason, the model was used in this study (French et al., 2013).

Marvin Weisbord's six-dimensional model is a framework for identifying that was introduced in 1976. This model shows to the agents of organizational change that for the diagnosis of organizational problems what places should be searched. Weisbord has identified six areas or very important parts (goals, structures, payments, mechanisms of coordination and control, relationships and leadership). In fact, these sectors are factors that organizations to achieve success must deal with them properly.

- Goals: What are we working on?
- Structure: How do we divide the work?
- Payment: Should all the tasks be encouraged?
- Useful mechanisms: Do we have enough technology coordination?
- Relationships: How we manage conflict between people? What technologies with?
- Leadership: Is there anyone who keeps these factors into equilibrium?

Weisbord recommends that before selecting the programs of creating change by exploring this six-dimensional model, we obtain general knowledge. To create a more comprehensive model for identifying the organizational

diagnosis, the component of attitude towards change has been added to the components of the model. This model answers the following question:

What are the major inconveniences of organizational change of the health adjutancy department based on Weisbord model?

Based on the above conceptual model, the research hypotheses were formulated in the following format:

Main hypothesis

There is some inconveniences in the health adjutancy department based on components of Weisbord's organizational change model.

Subsidiary hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is some inconveniences in the goals field of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 2: There is some inconveniences in the organizational structure field of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 3: There is some inconveniences in the leadership field of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 4: There is some inconveniences in the relationships system field of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 5: There is some inconveniences in the field of reward system and job promotion of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 6: There is some inconveniences in the useful mechanisms field of health adjutancy department.

Hypothesis 7: There is some inconveniences in the attitude towards change field of health adjutancy department.

Methodology

This research is an empirical research and with the aim of planning organizational change is carried out in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University. The present study, in terms of collecting data is descriptive and in terms of implementation method is survey (scrolling). Statistical population with the 176 participants is included all managers and experts working in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University. 109 participants out Of all the population were selected as the statistically sample by using random sampling method and Cochran formula. To ensure 117 questionnaires were distributed and finally 116 questionnaires were returned and the results were extracted based on them. In the present study, for collecting data was used from the field study and questionnaire tool. The questionnaire used in this study is the Weisbord's standard questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha method was used for the questionnaire reliability. For this purpose, first, they randomly distributed among 15 employees and then collecting, by using data obtained from the questionnaires and by using the SPSS statistical software were analyzed and Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated 90.4 which shows the high reliability of the questionnaire.

About the validity of the questionnaire can be said that our used questionnaire is the same Weisbord's standard questionnaire that has been carried out in many research and is used in Iranian organizations and approved. The results were presented as frequency, mean and standard deviation in descriptive stage; and in the analytical stage by using SPSS software from the t-test and ANOVA test were used.

Research findings

Descriptive results

Demographic characteristics of the study sample are as follows:

44.8 percent of the participants were female and the rest on them (55.2 %) were male. The mean and standard deviation of staff age is 7.08 ± 43.36 years and the mean and standard deviation of their work experience is 18.57 ± 6.64 years. Education degree of about 57 percent of employees is BA, 20.7 percent is MA, 19.8 percent is PhD and 2.6 percent is above diploma. 88.8 percent of employees were married and 11.2% were single.

Analytical results

Initially, normality of data distribution was evaluated by using kolmogrov-smirnov test and results showed that all dimensions have normally been distributed. So, parametric tests were used to analyze the data.

In the following graph and tables, present situation of the organizational aspects diagnosis in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University and its comparison with the optimal situation is provided.

Table 1: Mean of diagnosis score of organization dimensions in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Science University

Dimension	Number of samples	Mean	Standard deviation	T-statistics	Significance level
Goals	116	2.68	0.89	-15.81	0.000
Structure	116	3.25	1.07	-7.4	0.000
Leadership	116	2.95	1.03	-10.92	0.000
Relationships	116	2.88	0.85	-14	0.000
Rewards	116	3.84	1.18	-1.18	0.16
Useful mechanisms	116	3.11	0.94	-10.8	0.000
Attitude towards change	116	3.19	1.04	-8.23	0.000

Graph 1: Comparison of present situation of the organizational aspects diagnosis in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University with the optimal situation

As can be seen, according to the obtained results and based on Weisbord’s analytical model, dimensions of reward system and staff promotion are the most vulnerable organizational dimension and goals dimension has the most optimal situation relative to optimal situation.

In Table 2, those study components that based on the Weisbord model have the score of vulnerability greater than 3, in order of obtained score have been arranged.

Table 2: Components with the highest vulnerability amount

No.	Dimension	Component	Mean score
1	Reward and job promotion	There are the fairness and equity in criteria and measure of payments	4.63
2	Relationships	There is no conflict unresolved in the organization	4.52
3	Reward and job promotion	There is a balance between the received rights of person with the work that carries out in the organization	3.96
4	Attitude towards change	Lack of organization resistance against change	3.78
5	Reward and job promotion	Person career provides advancement opportunity for him in the organization	3.74
6	Useful mechanisms	There are adequate mechanisms for the integration of organization	3.73
7	Attitude towards change	Embracing change	3.68
8	Reward and job promotion	There is an opportunity for promotion in the organization	3.61
9	Structure	There is a flexibility for the work division in the organization	3.57
10	Useful mechanisms	Units help each other in times of need	3.56
11	Structure	Well-designed structure of staff work	3.55
12	Goals	Understand the priorities of the health adjutancy department objectives by staff working	3.48
13	Structure	rational division of labor duties	3.44
14	Reward and job promotion	All tasks are related with the incentives and motivations	3.3
15	Attitude towards change	enough familiarity with new policies and procedures	3.21
16	Leadership	Values and norms of the adjutancy leadership help the organization promotion	3.16

As can be seen, dimension of the reward and job promotion with 5 components, dimensions of the structure and attitude towards change each with 3 components, dimension of the useful mechanisms with 2 components and dimensions of the relationships, goals and leadership each with 1 component among vulnerable components have the highest and lowest share.

Discussion and conclusion

Hypothesis 1: There is some inconveniences in the goals field of health adjutancy department: Based on the results and interpretation of Weisbord's model ,in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, there isn't inconvenience in the goals dimension (mean = 2.68) and most of the

components have the mean score below 3 that shows relatively good situation of them in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University. Just, the employees perception of goals priorities component in the health adjutancy department, with mean of 3.48 showed that the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences in determining the goals priorities should act in such a way that is not created any ambiguity for staff.

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013) and Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011), Fatemeh Moghadam Koochi in Central Insurance of Iran (2010) and Vatankhah in teaching hospitals of Shiraz Medical Sciences University (2007).

Hypothesis 2: There is some inconveniences in the organizational structure field of health adjutancy department. Dimension of structure with a mean = 3.25 is in second place in terms of vulnerability. This dimension in the most components needs the attention and improvement. For example, in the three components from the five components of this dimension including flexibility in the division of labor in health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Science University (mean=3.57), good design of work structure of individuals (mean=3.55) and a reasonable division of work duties of individuals (mean=3.44) there is little agreement.

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Soudabeh Vatankhah in teaching hospitals of Shiraz Medical Sciences University (2007) and Safarany in hospitals related to Tehran Medical Sciences University (2011), that the majority of hospitals had weakness in the organizational structure. In most other studies such as Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013), Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011), Sepideh Masoud Sinaki in Tehran Medical Sciences University (2011), Fatemeh Moghadam Koochi in Central Insurance of Iran (2010) and Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009), inconvenience of mentioned dimension has been assessed on average.

Hypothesis 3: There is some inconveniences in the leadership field of health adjutancy department. Based on the results and interpretation of Weisbord's model ,in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, there isn't inconvenience in the leadership dimension with the mean = 2.59. However, the component of "values and norms of the leadership of this adjutancy help the organization promotion" with the mean of 3.16 showed that there is little agreement with the subject and should be done more review and research in this area and is determine that what values and norms are emphasized by the leadership of the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University that can't properly help the promotion of health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University.

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013) and Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011), Fatemeh Moghadam Koochi in Central Insurance of Iran (2010) and Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009). Inconvenience of mentioned dimension has been assessed on average. But in the research of Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009), Leadership has the most optimal situation and in other words, the dimension has the lowest vulnerability.

Hypothesis 4: There is some inconveniences in the relationships system field of health adjutancy department. In the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, there isn't inconvenience in the relationships dimension with the mean of 2.88. But, in this dimension, component of "Absence of conflict unresolved in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University" with the mean=4.52 showed that employees working in health departments disagree with this subject and believe that there are unresolved conflicts that can act as a barrier in the way of organization success.

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013) and Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009) that relationships is in second place in terms of the most optimal situation. But, in findings of Fazlollah Talebi in the Saderat Bank (2013), relationships system has been recognized the most vulnerable section and in the other research results of Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011), Sepideh Masoud Sinaki in Tehran Medical Sciences University (2011), Esmaeel Masoudian in the Shahid Rajae hospital of Gachsaran (2012), the dimension has the lowest vulnerability.

Hypothesis 5: There is some inconveniences in the field of reward system and job promotion of health adjutancy department. Based on the results and interpretation of Weisbord's model ,in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, dimension of reward and job promotion with the mean=3.84 needs the attention and improvement. In this dimension, all components have gained the score greater than 3 and need the attention and fair payment component with a mean=4.63 has the worst situation and needs the most attention. Next components that need attention are respectively as follows:

There is a balance between the received wage of person with the work that carries out in the organization (mean=3.96) Person job career provides advancement opportunity for him/her in the organization (mean= 3.74) There is an opportunity for promotion in the organization (mean =3.61) All tasks are related with the incentives and motivations (mean= 3.30).

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009), Fatemeh Moghadam Koochi in Central Insurance of Iran (2010), Sepideh Masoud Sinaki in Tehran Medical Sciences University (2011), Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011), Esmaeel Masoudian in the Shahid Rajae hospital of Gachsaran (2012), Fazlollah Talebi in the Saderat Bank (2013), Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013).

Hypothesis 6: There is some inconveniences in the useful mechanisms field of health adjutancy department. Based on the results and interpretation of Weisbord's model ,in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, there isn't serious inconvenience in the useful mechanisms dimension with the mean= 3.11 and is estimated on average but in some components needs the attention and improvement including components of "There are adequate mechanisms for the integration of organization" (mean=3.73) and "Units help each other in times of need "(mean = 3.56).

These two components are consistent with research conducted by Soudabeh Vatankhah in teaching hospitals of Shiraz Medical Sciences University (2007) and Esmaeel Masoudian in the Shahid Rajae hospital of Gachsaran (2012). But. In the research findings of Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013), useful mechanisms has the most vulnerable situation. Also, in two studies of Ali Shaemi Barzaki in Isfahan Medical Sciences University (2011) and Gholam Hossein Nikookar in Iran National carpet center (2009), this dimension after the reward dimension has the most vulnerable situation.

Hypothesis 7: There is some inconveniences in the field of attitude towards change of health adjutancy department. Based on the results and interpretation of Weisbord's model ,in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University, there isn't serious inconvenience in the dimension of attitude towards change with the mean=3.19 but it is in third place in terms of vulnerability and in the most components needs the attention and improvement. Lack of organization resistance against change (mean=3.78), embracing change (mean=3.68), enough familiarity with new policies and procedures (mean=3.21). In other words, most staff believe that the organization doesn't have a proper attitude to changes.

This finding is consistent with research conducted by Mohammad Hassan Moradi in Police (2013) that believes the attitude towards changes is in the second place in terms of vulnerability. But, this finding is not consistent with results obtained by Esmael Masoudian in the Shahid Rajaei hospital of Gachsaran (2012) and Soudabeh Vatankhah in teaching hospitals of Shiraz Medical Sciences University (2007) that according to it, all hospitals studied had a positive attitude towards change and readiness for change was in the optimal situation.

Suggestions

Recommendations based on analysis of “attitudes towards change” dimension:

Development and implementation of the mechanisms for updating the organization about new procedures and policies, establish the system of benchmarking within the organization, formulate and conduct the visit programs from the successful organizations in the organization development.

Recommendations based on analysis of “reward and job promotion” dimension:

- a- Optimize the payments system and create the dynamical system of payment with the following goals:
 - Create a fair payment system among employees
 - Create the positive and logical relationship between the performance of individuals and payments to them
- b- The proper evaluation of staff in order to allocate more rewarding to people with high work efficiency and comply their expectations
- c- Provide the job career for all employee and prepare the path of job promotion for staff

Recommendations based on analysis of “useful mechanisms” dimension:

Identification and comprehensive assessment of health adjutancy department Mashhad Medical Sciences University processes ,with the aim of integrating them (Remove the parallel processes and increase the efficient and effective accountability), organize the cross-sectional committees and work teams within the organization for Executing the organization programs.

Recommendations based on analysis of “leadership” dimension:

Identify and explain the values and norms of the organization's leaders, Review and institutionalize the transformational leadership and values of this kind of leadership in the organization

Recommendations based on analysis of “structure” dimension:

Design the logical model of the choice of health managers based on their knowledge and management experience and performance records, study and utilize the modern methods of organizing such adhocracy and etc., review and division of individuals tasks and duties .

Recommendations based on analysis of “communication” dimension:

Giving priority to training the conflict resolution skills for managers and employees, evaluate the effectiveness of communication channels within the organization.

Recommendations based on analysis of “goals” dimension:

Constitute the group dialogue sessions between management with organization departments, develop the appropriate communication policies, utilize the appropriate communication channels for the transmission of the organization's objectives priorities rather than notification and official correspondence.

As can be seen, this research has a wide range; therefore it is recommended that further studies be conducted on the following items:

- Organizational diagnosis with other models and comparison of results together
- Studying about optimum style of leadership and the development of core values in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University
- Studying barriers for creating the information integrity in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University and providing a mechanism for removing them.
- Studying efficiency and effectiveness of designed mechanisms in the organization and review them.
- Studying and identifying factors influencing on the attitude towards change and development.
- Studying the organizational culture and its relationship with change and development readiness in the health adjutancy department of Mashhad Medical Sciences University.

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